

A Lesson from Flannery O'Connor: The case of criminal justice reform

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Abstract

This article is the first to demonstrate how O'Connor embeds veiled public policy critiques within her fiction. By uncovering these implicit ideas, the study not only affirms O'Connor's intellectual and artistic depth but also underscores the interdisciplinary value of her work for scholars in sociology, political science, public policy, and beyond.

Reading Flannery O'Connor for Public Policy Reform

Critics have traditionally approached Flannery O'Connor's work from two main perspectives. The first group views her as a quintessential figure in the Southern Gothic tradition, often reducing her literary contributions to mere entertainment characterized by ironic twists and gratuitous violence. From this vantage point, her stories are seen as stylistic curiosities rather than works of serious intellectual merit.

The second group interprets O'Connor as a writer with a distinct theological mission. They regard her stories as modern-day Christian parables or allegories—carefully crafted moral commentaries on the spiritual condition of her era. In this view, O'Connor wields a prophetic voice, exposing the arrogance and complacency of the secular world, while also critiquing the apathy and hypocrisy within the Christian community.

However, a few other O'Connor critics go beyond the Gothic or the theological to understand the sociological merits of O'Connor's works. She is said to provide a penetrative insight into the habits and manners of her times. O'Connor is said to provide “throughout her fiction, a pervasive critique of religious, economic, and social structures” (Martin 56) and John May observes, O'Connor is “Audacious enough to judge the modern world with her own “pruning word”” (May xxiv). However, as Frederick Asals notes she does this without being didactic (Asals 228-229).

Furthermore, as Louis Rubin highlights O'Connor's sociological imagination and prophetic insights are striking:

She is important because her fiction affords us a perception of an aspect of the human situation that seems to me to be the most crucial just now, and into the nature of which she has provided some terrifying artistic insights. (Rubin 35)

The source O'Connor's "terrifying artistic insights" can be easily attributed to two crucial personal qualities her, namely her intellectual caliber and philosophical bend of mind. In this regard what Frederick Asals notes, "[I]t is clear from the finished stories and novels themselves that Flannery O'Connor was a highly conscious, intelligent—even "intellectual"—writer" (Asals 130) and Henry Edmonson adds, "Her literature is profoundly philosophical with vital theological implications" (Edmonson 5) are both noteworthy. Robert Coles also agrees with the assessment recognizing that O'Connor writes from a broad knowledge base: "She steeped herself in literature, of course; religion, of course; but also history and art and psychology and, in her own sharp fashion, the South's social and political matters" (Coles 111). That is why, we hear such striking statements about O'Connor as an author: "Few twentieth-century fiction writers seem more in need of interpretation and analysis than Flannery O'Connor" (May vii). If so, then O'Connor works demand discerning reading, and that is what some of her critics assert that meaning lurks behind her deceptively simplistic stories. Thomas Lorch says O'Connor is adept in "dropping meaning below the surface of the text" (Lorch 103) and Susan Sirgley notes O'Connor is "an author whose work reveals multiple layers of meaning available to the discerning reader" (Sirgley 29).

As much as O'Connor is noted for her intellectual acumen, her prophetic criticisms of the structures of society, and her skills to drop meaning below the surface that creates the reason to

explore her works in a new light to reveal additional insights from her oeuvre. This article explores her works in search of public policy ideas based on the logic that it is not likely that she presents a scathing criticism of society with her pruning words (May xxiv) at the same time suggesting solutions to the social problems her stories reflect. After all, according to the sociologist Lewis Coser it is not a farfetched attempt to look for insights about social problems in the works of accomplished literary artists:

The literary creator has the ability to identify with wide ranges of experiences, and he has the trained capacity to articulate through his fantasy the existential problems of his contemporaries. Why then should not sociology harness to its use, for the understanding of man and his society, those untapped sources in the rich accumulation of literature?

(Coser xvi)

It is based on Coser's observation regarding literature as a source place for sociological insights and what many have observed about O'Connor talented skills that this article analyzes two of her stories to demonstrate that Flannery O'Connor's stories do carry ideas about public policy. For a sample of her works, the article parses two stories, namely: "A Good Man is Hard to Find" and "A Temple of the Holy Ghost".

The case of “A Good Man is Hard to Find”

In her most famous short story, “A Good Man is Hard to Find, Flannery O'Connor follows a family road trip that ends in tragedy. A manipulative grandmother pressures her son into a detour, leading the family to a deserted road where they crash. They encounter an escaped convict known as The Misfit and his gang. As the Misfit's men kill the family one by one, the grandmother tries to appeal to his conscience. In a final moment of grace, she reaches out to him, calling him one of her own. He kills her anyway, highlighting the story's dark themes of grace, evil, and redemption.

Flannery O'Connor's “*A Good Man Is Hard to Find*” has long been interpreted through theological and existential lenses. Dominant readings emphasize either the story's meditation on nihilism—embodied in the character of the Misfit—or the moment of redemptive grace offered by the Grandmother, which the Misfit ultimately rejects. Critics generally categorize the story as a prime example of Southern Gothic fiction, marked by grotesque violence, ironic detachment, and a latent Christian moral arc. Within this framework, the Misfit is typically viewed as a postmodern anti-hero, spiritually and morally unmoored in an age that has lost its faith.

A few examples, from O'Connor and her scholars support this assertion.

“The Misfit has been equated with everyone from Christ to the devil to the Antichrist. [...]

O'Connor view the Misfit as a potential prophet (see MM 112-113)." (Cofer 55)

O'Connor says the Misfit is a prophet who lost his way; implying that the Misfit discerns something seriously wrong in society, but does the criticism by a deadly wrong means.

O'Connor's prophets are often marginalized from society, living on the fringes, isolating themselves either physically or through their bizarre and eccentric behavior.

The story is about of the absurdity of nihilism. O'Connor uses the Misfit to warn against the dangers of nihilism.

Stephen Bandy writes, "The Misfit's inability to believe has destroyed his humanity. His nihilism is complete: "No pleasure but meanness. [...] The Misfit lives in a world with no rules, a world in which "everything is permitted," including the ultimate crime of murder."

Douglas Leonard writes:

Many have seen the Misfit as the very personification of evil. His chosen name is obviously O'Connor's jab at certain liberal notions of antisocial behavior: the Misfit is not an otherwise good man who has been driven to crime by a political or existential alienation from his culture. Nor is he the product of a traumatic childhood. He is knowingly and willfully bad, as he himself contends: "It's nothing for you to do but enjoy the few minutes you got left the best way you can—by killing somebody or burning down his house or doing some other meanness to him" (p. 132). He is so bad that his reaction to the grandmother's love is violence. In O'Connor's terms: "This moment of grace excites the devil to frenzy. [Leonard 50]

However, this essay offers an alternative interpretation: that O'Connor subtly constructs the Misfit not merely as a metaphysical figure but as a symbol of systemic failure within the American justice system, particularly in the Jim Crow and post-Jim Crow South. Rather than being a philosophical nihilist by disposition alone, the Misfit is portrayed as a man whose life has been shaped—and ultimately deformed—by a judicial system that is arbitrary, dehumanizing, and indifferent to the plight of the marginalized.

A sociological focused interpretation of O'Connor's fiction is possible because her stories are representational or incarnational in style (Lorch 110, Leinard 281). More pertinently, "GMHF" is marked by representational art, because:

If the benchmark of good fiction is, as Flannery O'Connor claimed, a story that "hangs on and expands in the mind," then "A Good Man Is Hard to Find" has passed the litmus test since the definitive meanings have yet to be exhausted more than 50 years later (MM 108). [...] For O'Connor the frequently anthologized "A Good Man Is Hard to Find" is meant to serve as the magnum opus of her anagogical vision. (52)

Hence, given O'Connor's anagogical tendencies, taking the grandmother as the representation of the South would not be a far-fetched idea. I use the Grandmother as a metaphorical prism through which I will analyze the inter-generational, racial, class, and ideological conflicts besetting the South in the post-World War II years. In short, the grandmother becomes the South written small.

The Criminal Justice System

Based on the seriousness he recounts it, there are good reasons to take The Misfit's account of prison experience at face value. He says he suffered at the hand of the law out of proportion to what he has committed. There is little reason to subject him to months of solitary confinement for a crime he can barely remember for its insignificance. He bitterly laments his prison experience,

"Turn to the right, it was a wall," The Misfit said, looking up again at the cloudless sky. "Turn to the left, it was a wall. Look up it was a ceiling, look down it was a floor. I forget what I done, lady. I set there and set there, trying to remember what it was I done and I ain't recalled it to this day. Oncet in a while, I would think it was coming to me, but it never come." (CW 150)

Moreover, he finds the criminal justice system grossly distorted; he finds it a virtual unjust system. He pours out his heart to the grandmother: “Does it seem right to you, lady, that one is punished a heap and another ain't punished at all?” (CW 151)

Given what we know about the extent of wrongful convictions even today, it cannot be a farfetched idea that The Misfit could truly be a victim of a justice system that failed to function properly. Therefore, through The Misfit's narration, O'Connor subtly reminds society of the dire consequences of a failed criminal justice system, of courts which do not adequately protect the rights of the criminal defendant and are excessively punitive in their sentencing. Society which fails to maintain a well-functioning court and prison system can produce worse criminals it has received initially. Upon their release (or, prison escape as in the case of The Misfit), embittered inmates would exact revenge on society that they believe have treated them unjustly or in the first place has turned a blind eye to a grossly rigged criminal justice system. (See, for example, Lassete 230)ⁱ

On the other hand, the Misfit represents the second aspect of Southern society, whose sociological implication is visionary. The way the Misfit pours out his lamentations, he becomes a stinging critic of Southern society for an incompetent judicial system. For a crime that the Misfit claims he could not even recall committing, he says he has paid too much at the hand of the state. He says he could not square his harsh imprisonment with his alleged crime.

“Of Course,” he said, “they never shown me my papers. That’s why I sign myself now. I said long ago, you get you a signature and sign everything you do and keep a copy of it. Then you’ll know what you done and you can hold up the crime to the punishment and see do they match and in the end you’ll have something to prove you ain’t been treated right. I call myself The Misfit,” he said, “because I can’t make what all I done wrong fit what all I gone through in punishment.” (CW 151)

Apparently, because of his harsh punishment, which included solitary confinement, the Misfit has hardened against society. He wants to avenge himself; he wants society to teach a lesson about how to be careful about its justice system. After the Misfit has escaped his imprisonment, he unleashes a crime spree. Second time around, he makes sure that he leaves behind some written note trials, intending to own each crime he has committed. If caught, then he can square off his crime with his punishment.

Through this part of the Misfit's life, O'Connor wants us to see how a miscarriage of justice and harsh punishment could give rise to a radicalized individual who can cause harm to society once he leaves his prison. As in the case of the Misfit, if they can cloak their violence in their moral philosophy, they can perpetrate the most heinous crimes and can persist in their killing spree with little regrets.

The Question of the Misfit as a Reliable Narrator

Does the Misfit grumblings of the American justice system hold true to scrutiny? Is he an unreliable witness or narrator, or a symbol of a deep-seated problem?

O'Connor's use of grotesque characters often reflects societal flaws. The Misfit's extreme violence can be seen as the grotesque outcome of systemic failure, not merely an expression of his unreliable worldview. O'Connor's stories thrive on ambiguity and paradox. The Misfit's unreliability does not negate the validity of the social critique embedded in his narrative; it enhances the complexity of the story.

Even if the Misfit is unreliable, O'Connor deliberately places his complaints within the narrative, giving them thematic weight. Whether the Misfit is entirely reliable or not is beside the point. While the Misfit's behavior and worldview are deeply flawed, his descriptions of systemic failures (e.g., unjust trial and cruel prison conditions) are consistent and detailed. These elements appear to be less about exaggeration or manipulation and more about presenting his lived experience. The choice to include such detailed grievances about the justice system suggests that they are meant to resonate with the reader beyond the Misfit's personal story. What matters is that his complaints reflect a systemic problem that the justice system, society, and even religion have failed to address adequately.

What truly matters is how O'Connor forces readers to confront the question: What role does societal failure play in the making of individuals like the Misfit? It is such reframing of the story that can lead us to a more nuanced and enriching reading of the story that accounts for narrative complexity while drawing meaningful conclusions about the societal and systemic critiques in the story. However, the re-interpretation does not justify the Misfit's actions but examines the systemic failures that contributed to his development as a violent, alienated individual. This approach shifts the focus from the reliability of his character to the broader societal issues O'Connor critiques.

In conclusion, it can be admitted that the Misfit can simultaneously be an unreliable narrator in certain aspects (e.g., his interpretation of faith and morality) and a credible voice for exposing systemic injustices. O'Connor often uses contradictions to highlight complex truths, so this duality strengthens rather than undermines the key argument presented here.

The Misfit is not an isolated case but a fictional representation of a broader societal phenomenon. Numerous studies and reports demonstrate that harsh prison conditions and systemic injustices frequently produce individuals who are more damaged, bitter, or violent than when they entered the system. The Misfit's story reflects:

- **The Alienation of the Wrongfully Imprisoned:** Many individuals feel ostracized and hostile toward a society that has wronged them.
- **The Failure of Rehabilitation:** Prisons that emphasize punishment over reform often worsen criminal tendencies.
- **The Systemic Nature of the Problem:** The cycle of injustice is not limited to one individual but reflects systemic issues that persist across time and geography.

The following real-life examples show how systemic injustice and the cruelty of solitary confinement can foster resentment, alienation, and rage—parallels to the Misfit's journey. These sources lend credibility and contemporary relevance to your interpretation, framing the Misfit as a case study in systemic failure rather than a mere symbol of nihilism.

For example, the Harvard Political Review summarizes some of its key findings about the weaknesses of the American criminal justice system as follows:

Each year, more than 600,000 individuals are released from state and federal prisons.

Another nine million are released from local jails. Within three years of their release, two out of three former prisoners are rearrested and more than 50% are incarcerated again.

To put it plainly, unhealthy minds can't make healthy choices. The reality is 37% of incarcerated individuals and 44% of those in jail have been diagnosed with a mental health illness. Yet, 66% of prisoners reported not receiving any form of mental health care during the full length of their incarceration. [...] Our justice system has an obligation to prepare prisoners for a safe and successful reintegration, a process which starts with a healthy mind. [Harvard Political Review]

According to one BBC investigative report which is based on interviews conducted with former inmates notes:

[P]risoners described a process of “emotional numbing”. “It does harden you. It does make you a bit more distant,” one said, explaining how people in jail deliberately conceal and suppress their emotions. “It is who you become, and if you are hardened in the beginning then you become even harder, you become even colder, you become more detached.” Another prisoner stated: “It’s... I, kind of, don’t have feelings for people” any more.

The current evidence suggests that the longer and harsher the prison sentence – in terms of less freedom, choice and opportunity for safe, meaningful relationships – the more likely that prisoners’ personalities will be changed in ways that make their reintegration difficult and that increase their risk for re-offending.

Ultimately, society may be confronted with a choice. We can punish offenders more severely and risk changing them for the worse, or we can design sentencing rules and prisons in a way that helps offenders rehabilitate and change for the better. (The BBC))

The well-known novelist, John Grisham, in the book “Framed” which is dedicated to the life stories of ex-inmates who were wrongfully convicted writes:

“I have met many exonerees. As a group they are amazing because they somehow survived nightmares that the rest of us cannot begin to comprehend. All are determined to change a broken judicial system and prevent more wrongful convictions.” (John Grisham in “Framed” xi)

Ian Manuel, as a fourteen-year-old, was sentenced to life in prison without parole for a non-homicide crime. He spent close to twenty years in the Florida prison system, most of the years in solitary confinement and enduring inhumane conditions. He recalls the day he was placed in solitary confinement:

I was led down the hallway to 6 Charlie; I had no idea what 6 Charlie was, but it turned out to be solitary confinement. I was uncuffed and put into a single cell. It was brand new; the paint was so fresh you could smell it. It was cold there. They kept it cold there. That was OK. What disturbed me was everything was purple. The door was purple. The walls were purple. The rails were purple. The concrete slab that you put on your mattress was purple. [...] As to why everything was purple, psychologists had decided that the color had a calming effect on inmates. (Manuel, 61)

One instance of his torture in solitary confinement included:

“One day I was in my boxers sitting in my cell waiting for the nurse to bring me medication. Late at night my mind would race; I needed medication to grab and relax it so I could hit deep sleep. Instead I heard the clicking of the gas chain somewhere outside my door. This infernal device was like a fire extinguisher with an extended hose, and it has a distinctive sound that lets you know when the gas is coming. I did not know what was going on until Officer [X] and Seargent [Y] got to my cell’s flap. I heard Officer [X] laughing, letting me know outright that he hadn’t forgotten the bad blood between us. He sprayed me with a chemical agent through the flap. The kind of gas they used on me was clear; the heat it generated on my shirtless body was intense, fiery. It was as if I were standing in front of an oven blasting, its door open. I couldn’t get away from the pain for hours. I had to move constantly to lessen the hurt however slightly.

[...] Brutally terrorized at the hands of state employees, with no possibility of recourse, no one to come to my aid. I was reduced to my most basic elements; fighting for my basic existence; my most basic sense of dignity. I lost myself. I lost any hope I would ever go home, ever leave this prison. In my fiery rage and despair, I would immolate myself — literally, I wrapped myself in newspaper and set myself on fire.

[...] It was at this juncture that the toll of long-term solitary confinement would begin to be felt most acutely and self-destructively. My life had shrunk to the size of an eight-by-ten cell. And my preoccupation became defending that cell and the shadow of life remaining to me. Within that space — both physical and mental — I turned on my own body and began cutting myself, as I saw numerous others in confinement do. (Manuel, 111-112)

Moreover, like the Misfit, Ian Manuel, has a quibble against the head doctors (i.e., psychiatrists) whom he sees as some form of accomplice in the unjust criminal justice system.

On February 22, 1991, my lawyer had told the judge that there were aspects of my background that called my competency to stand trial into question. According to the law, if a defendant's competency is questioned before the court, the judge must order an evaluation, which he did in my case. But the judge did not hold a hearing to determine my competency as required. Two psychiatrists did in fact examine me and said I was fit, even as they called me a sociopath — but not in an open hearing with a declaration by the judge. (Manuel, 140-141)

Likewise, the Misfit insists that he was convicted without a clear explanation of his crime and subjected to long-term solitary confinement, a carceral practice widely condemned by human rights organizations for its psychological harm. These experiences are not peripheral details; they are central to his identity and motivations. His name itself—“The Misfit”—encapsulates his alienation from a social and legal order that failed to recognize or rehabilitate him. In this light, the Misfit's violent rejection of the Grandmother's overtures can be read not merely as a refusal of spiritual grace but as an expression of his disillusionment with a society that cloaks its injustices in Christian morality. The Grandmother represents this moral contradiction: a woman who professes piety and traditional values yet shows little real understanding or empathy. She appeals to the Misfit's supposed inner goodness, but her words fall flat, possibly because he associates her religious language with the very social institutions—church, court, and prison—that have crushed him.

There is a necessary soul-searching that needs to occur how to handle the criminal offender. The kind of questions Michael Dow Burkhead raises in his book, “The Treatment of Criminal

Offenders” are part of this ongoing soul searching. The aim is to find the middle ground between punishment and amendment, protecting society and rehabilitating the offender:

Should we make offenders suffer or should we help them? Which is the most effective for ensuring our safety? Which is more just? Which is more human? Can we do both at once, as some have claimed?

[...] We often complain that it is lack of knowledge which prevents our progress in reducing crime and recidivism, but it is, instead, our deeply conflicted feelings about punishment and treatment which impede us. We must move this great debate beyond the primitive urge for revenge and place it above the poisoned dialogue of partisan politics. We have had, from the beginning, more light than we have used and perhaps we will not be gaining any new insights until we have learned to use what we already know.

(Burkhead 180)

Conclusion

This study shows how the new approach invites us to consider “*A Good Man Is Hard to Find*” as more than a spiritual parable; it is a prescient warning about the consequences of a punitive and unequal justice system. O’Connor anticipates, through fiction, the insights later confirmed by decades of criminological and sociological research: that prisons, particularly those employing solitary confinement, often produce not repentance but rage, not rehabilitation but irreparable psychic damage. The Misfit is not merely “evil” in the abstract; he is a man profoundly shaped by a system that punished without understanding and confined without healing.

In a broader context, O'Connor's story functions as a critique of Southern religiosity intertwined with legal injustice—an unholy alliance that perpetuates violence rather than redemption. In this reading, the violence at the story's end is not gratuitous but cautionary: it dramatizes the predictable outcome of a justice system that forsakes the very values—mercy, dignity, equity—it claims to uphold.

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¹ See, for example, The National Registry of Exonerations
(<http://www.law.umich.edu/special/exoneration/Pages/about.aspx>), for modern cases of wrongful convictions.